

Longitudinal Self-Monitoring of Physical Condition Under Continued Self-Care: A Single Case Report

Takahashi. M

Independent researcher

Correspondence: takahashi.m.contact@gmail.com

Abstract

Objective : This study exploratorily examined temporal changes and interrelations of physiological and subjective symptom indicators under continuous self-care in a single-participant self-observation design. In addition, photographic documentation of back skeletal alignment was collected as reference material, and observation of the external auditory canal was performed to assess the measurement accuracy of a tympanic thermometer.

Methods : Over approximately 4.5 months, the participant recorded left and right tympanic temperatures, axillary body temperature, subjective head heat sensation, pain, fatigue, and lemborexant dose. During the last 1.5 months, subjective psychological distress and sternocleidomastoid tension scores were additionally recorded. Photographs of back skeletal alignment were taken irregularly. Pearson's correlation evaluated associations between bilateral mean tympanic temperatures and other indicators, while Spearman's rank correlation evaluated ordinal measurement order and repeated measures. Multiple testing was corrected using the Benjamini–Hochberg method.

Results : Bilateral mean tympanic temperatures showed a positive correlations with subjective head heat sensation scores, and positive correlations were also observed with axillary body temperature, pain scores, and fatigue scores. The measurement order variable showed positive correlations with head heat sensation scores, pain scores, and fatigue scores. Lemborexant dose exhibited a negative correlation with elapsed days. External auditory canal observations and back alignment photos were shown as exploratory materials, without statistical analysis.

Conclusions : In this exploratory N=1 study, it was possible to describe the overall physical condition from multiple perspectives, which might be difficult to capture using symptom scores alone. These results are descriptive and hypothesis-generating, and their generalizability is limited.

Introduction

This case involved a middle-aged adult female who had experienced prolonged and severe fatigue, pain, sleep disturbances, and brain fog. As part of her daily coping strategies for these symptoms, she had been consistently performing stretching and light manual massage (conventional self-care) even before the observation period, and had begun a more structured electric massage using a commercially available massager approximately 10 months prior to the start of the observation period. Subsequently, noticing increases in her tympanic temperature amid daily fluctuations in her physical condition prompted her to begin systematically recording both physiological and subjective indicators.

In this case, it was considered that bodily discomfort might exist that could not be fully captured by single symptom indicators such as pain or fatigue alone. Therefore, information from multiple dimensions—including tympanic temperature, subjective symptom scores, photographic records of skeletal alignment, and diary entries—was collected concurrently. In addition, to verify the reliability of tympanic temperature measurements, observation of the external auditory canal was conducted using a camera-equipped ear pick.

The aim of this study was not to evaluate specific intervention effects or test pathophysiological hypotheses, but rather to record and describe, as faithfully as possible, the fluctuations in physical condition that occurred during daily life, including self-care such as massage. In addition, this study did not aim to classify the case into a specific diagnostic category, but was an exploratory attempt to report the temporal changes in symptoms descriptively. This case report involved the author herself and included long-term self-observation records conducted under circumstances where regular visits to medical institutions were difficult. The ability to capture fluctuations that are difficult to observe in outpatient visits or cross-sectional evaluations represents one potential contribution of this case report.

Case Presentation

This case involved a middle-aged adult female who had experienced prolonged fatigue, pain, sleep disturbances, and brain fog. Her fatigue had gradually intensified since adolescence and persisted for approximately ten years, during which she also experienced a variety of other physical symptoms. Upon reaching adulthood, she developed new widespread pain and a sense of bodily tension perceived as muscle tension, which began to interfere with daily life and work. Although she underwent continuous examinations and consultations at multiple

medical institutions, no clear organic abnormalities were identified. She also tried psychiatric visits and pharmacological treatments, but her symptoms did not improve sufficiently, and ultimately, attending medical visits became difficult.

Under circumstances where attending medical visits was difficult, she continued stretching and light manual massage as part of her daily coping strategies (conventional self-care). In addition, beginning approximately 10 months before the start of the observation period, she also regularly performed electric massage using a commercially available massager. Initially, the massage was primarily assisted by family members, but she later performed it herself using the electric massager, maintaining it as a daily routine. Details regarding the observation period and measured variables are provided in the Methods section.

Methods

1. Study Design

This study was a prospective single-case observational study. The participant was the author herself, and longitudinal recording and analysis were conducted to capture temporal changes in symptoms and physiological indicators under real-world daily living conditions.

At the start of the observation period, electric massage had already been ongoing, and the data analyzed in this study were obtained from approximately 10 months after the initiation of electric massage onward. Therefore, this study was not designed to compare pre- and post-electric massage periods or to examine causal relationships, but rather as an observational study aimed at descriptively capturing temporal fluctuations in symptom scores and other indicators under self-care, including electric massage. All self-care and measurements were performed as part of daily life, and strict standardization of massage or measurement conditions was not implemented.

In this study, it was considered that bodily discomfort might exist that could not be fully captured by single symptom indicators such as pain or fatigue, and therefore, indicators from different dimensions were collected concurrently. Specifically, tympanic temperature, subjective symptom scores, photographic records of skeletal alignment, and diary entries were used. These measurements were not intended to assume any specific pathophysiological mechanism, but rather aimed to describe temporal fluctuations in physical condition from multiple perspectives.

During the first half of the observation period, tympanic temperature, axillary body temperature, subjective head heat sensation scores, fatigue scores, pain scores, and lemborexant dose were primarily recorded. As the observation progressed, recording of sternocleidomastoid tension scores and subjective psychological distress scores was added. Photographs of the back for evaluating skeletal alignment were obtained irregularly whenever feasible given daily living circumstances. In addition, to confirm the procedural validity of tympanic temperature measurements, observation of the external auditory canal was also conducted using a camera-equipped ear pick.

Observations and recordings in this study are still ongoing; however, for the purposes of the present analysis, only data obtained up to the time of manuscript preparation over a defined period were analyzed. The selection of the analysis period was based on practical considerations, including the author's physical capacity and constraints in daily life.

2. Participant

The participant was a single middle-aged adult female experiencing chronic fatigue, pain, sleep disturbances, and brain fog. This study represents a self-case report (N=1 study), and no classification based on specific medical diagnoses was performed. Daily fluctuations in physical condition and subjective sensations were recorded as faithfully as possible.

3. Use of Commercial Handheld Electric Vibrating Massagers

In this case, two types of handheld electric vibrating massagers were used as part of self-care. Neither device was a medical device; both were commercially available to general consumers and featured multiple levels of vibration intensity.

At the start of the observation period, a device manufactured by LIHILIS (model number unknown) was used. The vibration intensity was gradually increased according to the participant's subjective perception of stimulation; however, this was not an intervention based on the study protocol, but rather part of her routine self-care. Approximately two months after the start of the observation period, the device was switched to the MYTREX REBIVE EX PRO (model EH011FYT, manufactured by Sotsu Medical Co., Ltd.). Thereafter, this device was used, similarly, the intensity was gradually increased from a low level.

Throughout the observation period, the massage targeted the entire body surface, and neither the treatment sites nor the order of application were fixed; areas with stronger pain or stiffness were prioritized. Each site was massaged for approximately 5–10 minutes, with a total session lasting 30 minutes to 1 hour, performed once or twice daily (mainly in the morning and night). The number of sessions and vibration intensity were adjusted as needed based on the effects of the previous day's massage. In addition to self-administered electric massage, stretching and supplementary massage by family members were also performed; however, the majority of the time was devoted to handheld electric massage.

4. Measured Variables and Observation Period

4.1 Overview of Measurement Schedule from the Start of Electric Massage

The measurement schedule during the observation period for this case is shown in Table 1. Elapsed time is indicated relative to the start of electric massage. Variables collected over approximately 4.5 months included tympanic temperature, subjective head heat sensation scores, pain scores, fatigue scores, and lemborexant dose, which were recorded on most days during the observation period. In addition, axillary body temperature was measured as a supplementary variable and was used primarily to assess short-term relationships with tympanic temperature. Several additional variables were introduced during the latter part of the observation period and were collected over approximately 1.5 months. These included sternocleidomastoid tension scores and subjective psychological distress scores.

Changes in tympanic temperature before and after bathing were also measured during the observation period; however, the analysis methods and details are provided in the supplementary material. Complete data across the entire period do not exist, but measurements were obtained as continuously as possible within practical limits. Detailed methods for measuring each variable are described in the corresponding sections.

Observations and recordings in this study are still ongoing; however, for the purposes of this paper, only data obtained up to the time of manuscript preparation over a defined period were analyzed.

Table 1. Elapsed Time and Measurement Schedule Relative to the Start of Electric Massage

Time Point	Description
Approximately 10 years	Irregular performance of conventional self-care (stretching and light manual massage)
Start of electric massage	Initiation of massage using a commercially available handheld electric vibrating massager (LIHILIS)
About 2 weeks later	Start of back photography (continued irregularly)
About 10 months later	Start of longitudinal measurements collected over ~4.5 months
About 10.5 months later	Start of measuring tympanic temperature changes before and after bathing
About 12 months later	Change of massage device to MYTREX REBIVE EX PRO (Sotsu Medical Co., Ltd.)
About 13 months later	Introduction of additional variables collected over ~1.5 months
About 14.5 months later	End of observation period

In this study, self-regulatory behaviors not involving electric devices, such as stretching or light manual massage, are referred to as “conventional self-care,” while interventions using commercially available electric massagers are referred to as “electric massage.” In contexts where both are collectively addressed, the term “self-care” is used. Furthermore, in this study, the term “muscle tension” is used solely for convenience to describe the participant’s subjective perception of bodily tension or stiffness and does not denote any specific physiological state. Identifying the underlying mechanisms is not an objective of this study.

4.2 Variables Measured Over Approximately 4.5 Months

4.2.1 Tympanic Temperature

Tympanic temperature was measured three times daily (morning, noon, and night). For each ear, the mode of 2–3 measurements was adopted as the left and right tympanic temperatures, and the average of both ears was calculated and analyzed as the bilateral mean tympanic temperature. A Pigeon ear infrared thermometer (“Mimi Chibion,” model HA03D; Pigeon Corporation) was used. A dedicated probe cover was attached during measurements, and all

measurements were performed using the same device.

During the observation period, the probe cover was replaced multiple times. The date of the first replacement was unknown, while the second replacement date was identified based on diary records. Therefore, all data obtained during the approximately 1-week period preceding the second replacement were excluded from the analysis. Thereafter, measurements continued with probe cover replacements approximately once a month.

4.2.2 Axillary Body Temperature

Axillary body temperature was measured irregularly to exclude systemic fever caused by conditions such as colds. Specifically, axillary temperature was always measured at least once whenever tympanic temperature showed elevated values, and for a limited period of approximately 1 week, measurements were taken three times daily (morning, noon, and night). A commercially available electronic thermometer (Terumo Electronic Thermometer C230, serial number 11-G24A) was used, and all measurements were performed using the same device.

4.2.3 Symptom Scores (Subjective Head Heat Sensation, Fatigue, and Pain Scores)

Each symptom was assessed using a 0–10 subjective scale and recorded three times daily (morning, noon, and night).

Subjective Head Heat Sensation Score: Subjective perception of heat sensation at the center of the head. 0 indicates no heat sensation, and 10 indicates the strongest heat sensation.

Fatigue Score: Overall bodily fatigue. 0 indicates no fatigue, and 10 indicates an almost immobile state.

Pain Score: Covers pain throughout the body, including pain at rest, pain during movement, and sensory hypersensitivity. 0 indicates no pain, and 10 indicates the most severe pain. The pain score comprehensively assessed all pain perceived in daily life, including pain in the arms, legs, and trunk, as well as abdominal pain, headache, ocular pain, and other types or origins of pain, without distinguishing among different types or anatomical locations of pain.

4.2.4 Recording of Lemborexant dose

In this case, lemborexant (Dayvigo) was taken as a sleep medication. The dose was either 2.5 mg or half a tablet (1.25 mg), and 0 mg was recorded on days when the medication was not taken. Daily doses were adjusted based on the participant's subjective symptoms.

4.2.5 Diary

The diary was not recorded every day, but daily life events such as changes in physical condition, outings, or demanding schedules, as well as physical and mental changes, and observations related to symptoms or self-care, were recorded as notes as needed. These diary entries were used solely as qualitative reference information to contextualize the observation period and to confirm procedural details (e.g., probe cover replacement timing), and were not included in quantitative analyses. Other symptoms recorded in the diary, such as headaches, abdominal discomfort, increased urinary frequency, ocular pain, and small raised rashes, were not individually quantified or included in the analysis due to inconsistent frequency and variability in severity.

4.3 Additional Variables Collected Over Approximately 1.5 Months

The latter measured variables were obtained only during the latter approximately 1.5 months of the observation period and were used for exploratory analyses. Each variable was assessed using a 0–10 subjective scale and recorded three times daily (morning, noon, and night).

Sternocleidomastoid tension score: The sternocleidomastoid muscle was chosen as a representative indicator of muscle tension because it is easily palpable from the body surface and its tension changes are easily perceived in daily life. The score evaluated muscle stiffness, resting tension or tightness, and restrictions or pain associated with neck movement. 0 indicates no tension, and 10 indicates severe tension.

Subjective Psychological Distress Score: This score assessed the participant's perceived psychological distress. 0 indicates no distress, and 10 indicates a state of strong feelings of despair or sadness.

4.4 Tympanic Temperature and Visual Changes in the External Auditory Canal

During tympanic temperature measurements, when the correspondence between measured values and symptom score trends was not always clear, the probe cover of the ear thermometer was replaced to verify measurement conditions. If the relationship between measured values and symptom scores remained difficult to interpret, additional verification was performed by observing the external auditory canal using a camera-equipped ear pick.

Observations of the external auditory canal were performed not only during periods when the relationship between symptom scores and measured values was unclear, but also on several occasions when the measured values were considered relatively stable, serving as a reference for comparison. The assessment of the clarity of correspondence between measured values and symptom scores was not defined statistically, but was based on the participant's subjective judgment from longitudinal observation.

In this study, images of the external auditory canal were captured using a commercially available camera-equipped ear pick (manufacturer unknown; consumer product). This device was not intended for diagnostic purposes as a medical instrument, and the images were used to examine potential sources of measurement error and as a visual reference. Although the recording was performed in video format, still images from representative locations were used for discussion in this study.

4.5 Evaluation of Skeletal Alignment (Photographic Recording)

Back photographs were taken at irregular intervals during the observation period. Photographs were captured in the same posture and under consistent conditions, and skin surface details and surrounding visual information that could lead to personal identification were removed during analysis. After extracting the contour of the back, lateral trunk asymmetry and lateral deviation of the spine were assessed visually and through angular measurements. A reference line approximating the spinal axis was defined as a straight line drawn along the visually identified alignment of the spinous processes on the back contour image. Angles of the cervical, thoracic, and lumbar segments were defined as the angles formed between straight-line approximations of adjacent spinal segments. For surface-based indices, straight lines were drawn between predefined anatomical landmarks (e.g., inferior angles of the scapulae, bilateral lateral abdominal contour inflection points, and the highest points of the iliac crests), and the angles between these lines and a horizontal reference line defined by the image frame were measured directly on the image. This approach was regarded

as an exploratory and supplementary assessment and was not intended to represent standardized clinical measurements such as radiographic Cobb angles.

Photographic recordings began approximately 1 month after the start of electric massage, and a total of 10 photographs were obtained by the end of the observation period. In the main text, photographs taken approximately 1 month, 6 months, and 14.5 months after the start of electric massage are presented as representative examples. Because some photographs were taken prior to the start of body temperature and symptom score recordings, they were not used for statistical analysis and are presented as supplementary indicators illustrating temporal changes in skeletal morphology. This method was intended to examine the feasibility of a simple self-observation approach and was not intended for clinical diagnosis.

4.6 Measurement Conditions for Indicators Recorded Three Times Daily

Tympanic temperature and subjective scores (head heat sensation, fatigue, pain, sternocleidomastoid tension, and subjective psychological distress) were measured three times daily (immediately after waking, around noon, and at night). Because waking times were not consistent, the morning measurement was taken immediately after waking, while the noon and night measurements were approximately 12:00 and 19:00, respectively. Measurements were conducted under daily living conditions, and factors such as resting state, meal timing, and room temperature were not strictly standardized. The measurement protocol was designed to minimize burden and prioritize feasibility for sustained longitudinal observation.

5. Statistical Analysis

Correlation analyses and longitudinal analyses were conducted only during periods in which the respective indicators were measured concurrently. No statistical analyses were performed for indicators whose measurement periods did not overlap.

5.1 Statistical Software and Analysis Approach

Analyses were performed using R (EZR, version 4.3.1). In this study, p-values and FDR-adjusted q-values are reported as observed, serving as supplementary numerical information to describe the magnitude and consistency of associations. These values were not intended for making formal determinations of statistical significance.

5.2 Correlation Analysis Among Multiple Indicators Including Tympanic Temperature

Associations between bilateral mean tympanic temperature and each indicator obtained during the approximately 4.5-month observation period (subjective head heat sensation score, fatigue score, pain score, and lemborexant dose) were evaluated using Pearson's correlation coefficients (r).

For the approximately 1.5-month period during which additional variables were collected, associations between bilateral mean tympanic temperature and the sternocleidomastoid tension score as well as the subjective psychological distress score were analyzed using the same method.

Only paired observations for which corresponding measurements were available at the same time point were included in the analyses. Because symptom scores were measured three times daily, values recorded at the same time of day were paired for correlation analyses with tympanic temperature. In contrast, because lemborexant dose was recorded once daily (at night), analyses were conducted by pairing the nightly dose with the corresponding nighttime measurements. Differences in measurement frequency and observation periods among indicators are described in the previous section.

Furthermore, to characterize the overall correlation structure among the indicators, a 10×10 correlation matrix was constructed including the following variables: left tympanic temperature, right tympanic temperature, bilateral mean tympanic temperature, axillary body temperature, subjective head heat sensation score, pain score, fatigue score, sternocleidomastoid tension score, subjective psychological distress score, and lemborexant dose. The overall correlation matrix is presented in the Supplementary Materials. Correlation coefficients were calculated using all available paired observations for each variable pair; therefore, effective sample sizes varied across matrix elements due to differences in measurement periods and missing data. Because the mutual correlations among left, right, and bilateral mean tympanic temperatures were considered to exhibit high informational redundancy, these correlations were not considered substantively informative.

Regarding tympanic temperature, it was later considered possible that measurements obtained during a period in which the probe cover of the ear thermometer had not been replaced might have been systematically lower. Therefore, data from this approximately 1-week period were excluded from all analyses. The same exclusion criteria were consistently applied to all analyses involving tympanic temperature.

The pre–post bathing temperature change, defined as the difference between pre- and post-bathing temperatures, was measured once daily and is inherently dependent on the pre-bathing temperature. Therefore, it was not included in the correlation matrix analysis. A separate analysis adjusting for the influence of pre-bathing temperature was conducted, and the details are provided in the Supplementary Materials.

5.3 Correlation Analysis Between Three-Times-Daily Measured Indicators and the Measurement Order Variable

The morning measurement on the first day of recording was coded as 1, the noon measurement as 2, and the nighttime measurement as 3. Subsequent measurements were sequentially numbered to generate a continuous time-order variable.

Using this time-order variable, monotonic temporal trends were evaluated using Spearman's rank correlation coefficient for the following indicators measured three times daily: left tympanic temperature, right tympanic temperature, bilateral mean tympanic temperature, axillary body temperature, subjective head heat sensation score, pain score, fatigue score, sternocleidomastoid tension score, and subjective psychological distress score. For visualization of the time-series graphs, the median of the morning, noon, and nighttime measurements for each day was used to enhance readability, and the x-axis was expressed as elapsed days.

In addition, boxplots stratified by time of day (morning, noon, and night) were generated to descriptively assess differences in the distributions of these indicators according to measurement time. These analyses were not intended for formal statistical testing, and the results are presented in the Supplementary Materials.

5.4 Correlation Analysis Between Lemborexant Dose and Elapsed Days

Because lemborexant dose was recorded once daily, its association with elapsed days was evaluated using Spearman's rank correlation coefficient.

5.5 Adjustment for Multiple Comparisons

Adjustment for multiple comparisons was performed using the Benjamini–Hochberg procedure for analyses involving multiple simultaneous correlation tests (i.e., the 10×10 correlation matrix and the correlation analyses between the three-times-daily measured indicators and the measurement order variable). In contrast, the multiple regression analysis concerning the pre–post bathing temperature change was conducted as an exploratory supplementary analysis and, given its exploratory nature, was not subjected to adjustment for multiple comparisons.

5.6 Handling of Missing Data

Missing values were excluded from the analyses, and each analysis was conducted using only the available data for the respective indicator. The analysis periods and the extent of missing data are described in the Methods section.

6. Ethical Considerations (Self-Case Study)

This study was a self-case study conducted on the author and was not intended for medical practice, diagnosis, or treatment. Long-term longitudinal self-observation was performed to document physical condition, pain, muscle tension, and skeletal alignment during daily life under ongoing self-care, including the use of an electric massage device. The electric massage had been voluntarily performed by the author prior to the initiation of this study and was not newly introduced for therapeutic purposes at the start of the research.

The study design, data recording, analysis, and publication were conducted based on the author's full understanding and voluntary participation. No personally identifiable information has been disclosed, and only limited background information has been provided in the case description. In reporting and academically disseminating this case, careful attention was paid to anonymization.

Results

1. Association Between Tympanic Temperature and Symptom / Behavioral Indicators

The associations between bilateral mean tympanic temperature and each indicator were evaluated using Pearson's correlation coefficient. The results are shown in Table 2. A positive association was descriptively observed between bilateral mean tympanic temperature and subjective head heat sensation score ($r = 0.591$, 95% CI 0.518–0.655, $p = 1.32 \times 10^{-34}$, $q = 1.39 \times 10^{-33}$). Positive associations were also descriptively observed between bilateral mean tympanic temperature and axillary body temperature, pain score, and fatigue score. In contrast, no clear associations was observed between bilateral mean tympanic temperature and subjective psychological distress score or lemborexant dose.

In this analysis, the degrees of freedom (df) were calculated based on the number of available paired measurements obtained at the same time point for each indicator. A 10×10 correlation matrix summarizing the correlation coefficients among the principal indicators is provided in the Supplementary Materials.

Table 2. Correlation Coefficients Between Bilateral Mean Tympanic Temperature and Body Temperature/Symptom Indicators (Exploratory Analysis)

Indicator	Correlation Coefficient (r)	95% CI	p-value	q-value (FDR-adjusted)	df
Axillary body temperature	0.367	0.173–0.533	3.76×10^{-4}	9.29×10^{-4}	88
Subjective head heat sensation score	0.591	0.518–0.655	1.32×10^{-34}	1.39×10^{-33}	351
Pain score	0.177	0.074–0.276	8.34×10^{-4}	1.59×10^{-3}	351
Fatigue score	0.269	0.170–0.363	2.80×10^{-7}	1.06×10^{-6}	351
Sternocleido mastoid tension score	-0.051	-0.242–0.144	0.611	0.694	101
Subjective mental distress score	-0.114	-0.301–0.081	0.250	0.350	101
Lemborexant dose	-0.020	-0.200 – 0.162	0.832	0.896	116

Note: Exploratory analyses evaluating the associations between bilateral mean tympanic temperature and each indicator using Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) are presented. The p-values and FDR-adjusted q-values are reported as observed values for descriptive purposes and were not used as criteria for determining statistical significance. The degrees of freedom (df) correspond to each individual correlation analysis.

Next, the temporal changes in tympanic temperature and each indicator (fatigue score, pain score, subjective head heat sensation score, and lemborexant dose) were plotted over time and are shown in Figures 1–4.

For variables measured three times per day (left, right, and bilateral mean tympanic temperature; subjective head heat sensation score; fatigue score; pain score; sternocleidomastoid tension score; subjective psychological distress score ; and axillary temperature during part of the study period), the median value of each day was used as the representative value to improve visual clarity. Missing data in the latter part of the tympanic temperature record resulted from the exclusion of measurements obtained before replacement of the probe cover.

Figure 1. Temporal Changes in Bilateral Mean Tympanic Temperature and Subjective Head Heat Sensation Score

Note: Bilateral mean tympanic temperature and subjective head heat sensation score were measured three times per day, and the median value for each day was plotted as the representative value in consideration of visual clarity. Missing data in the latter part of the tympanic temperature record are due to the exclusion of measurements obtained before replacement of the probe cover. This graph represents observations from a single case, and temporal trends may be influenced by symptoms and measurement conditions.

Figure 2. Temporal Changes in Bilateral Mean Tympanic Temperature and Pain Score

Note: Bilateral mean tympanic temperature and pain score were measured three times per day, and the median value for each day was plotted as the representative value in consideration of visual clarity. Missing data in the latter part of the tympanic temperature record are due to the exclusion of measurements obtained before replacement of the probe cover. This graph represents observations from a single case, and temporal trends may be influenced by symptoms and measurement conditions.

Figure 3. Temporal Changes in Bilateral Mean Tympanic Temperature and Fatigue Score

Note: Bilateral mean tympanic temperature and fatigue score were measured three times per day, and the median value for each day was plotted as the representative value in consideration of visual clarity. Missing data in the latter part of the tympanic temperature record are due to the exclusion of measurements obtained before replacement of the probe cover. This graph represents observations from a single case, and temporal trends may be influenced by symptoms and measurement conditions.

Figure 4. Temporal Changes in Bilateral Mean Tympanic Temperature and Daily Lemborexant Dose

Note: Bilateral mean tympanic temperature was measured three times per day, and the median value for each day was plotted as the representative value in consideration of visual clarity. Lemborexant dose was recorded once per day, and no missing data were observed. Missing data in the latter part of the tympanic temperature record are due to the exclusion of measurements obtained before replacement of the probe cover. This graph represents observations from a single case, and temporal trends may be influenced by symptoms and measurement conditions.

2. Correlation Analysis Between Three-Times-Daily Measured Indicators and the Measurement Order Variable

The correlations between the measurement order variable (sequentially numbered with the morning of the first recording day coded as 1, noon as 2, and night as 3) and the three-times-daily measured indicators were evaluated using Spearman's rank correlation coefficient. The results are shown in Table 3.

Positive associations with the measurement order variable were descriptively observed for subjective head heat sensation score ($\rho = 0.258$, $p = 1.95 \times 10^{-7}$, $q = 5.85 \times 10^{-7}$), pain score ($\rho = 0.644$, $p = 7.49 \times 10^{-48}$, $q = 6.74 \times 10^{-47}$), and fatigue score ($\rho = 0.383$, $p = 2.72 \times 10^{-15}$, $q = 1.22 \times 10^{-14}$).

In contrast, no clear associations were observed for left or right tympanic temperature, bilateral mean tympanic temperature, sternocleidomastoid tension score, or subjective psychological distress score.

The sternocleidomastoid tension score and subjective psychological distress score were measured only during the latter approximately 1.5 months of the observation period. Missing values for tympanic temperature were concentrated in the latter part of the observation period, whereas axillary body temperature had a relatively high proportion of missing data throughout the entire period.

Table 3. Spearman’s Rank Correlation Coefficients Between Three-Times-Daily Measured Indicators and the Measurement Order Variable

Indicator	ρ	p-value	q-value (FDR-adjusted)	Analysis Period
Left tympanic temperature	0.058	0.274	0.411	Approximately 4.5 months (continuous measurement)
Right tympanic temperature	-0.012	0.823	0.823	Approximately 4.5 months (continuous measurement)
Bilateral mean tympanic temperature	0.025	0.634	0.716	Approximately 4.5 months (continuous measurement)
Subjective head heat sensation score	0.258	1.95×10^{-7}	5.85×10^{-7}	Approximately 4.5 months (continuous measurement)
Pain score	0.644	7.49×10^{-48}	6.74×10^{-47}	Approximately 4.5 months (continuous measurement)
Fatigue score	0.383	2.72×10^{-15}	1.22×10^{-14}	Approximately 4.5 months (continuous measurement)
Axillary body temperature	-0.283	0.006	0.014	Approximately 4.5 months (substantial missing data)
Sternocleidomastoid tension score	0.099	0.241	0.411	Measured only during the latter approximately 1.5 months
Subjective psychological distress score	0.04	0.636	0.716	Measured only during the latter approximately 1.5 months

Note: Exploratory analyses evaluating the associations between each indicator and the measurement order variable using Spearman’s rank correlation coefficient (ρ) are presented. The p-values and FDR-adjusted q-values are reported as observed values for descriptive reference and were treated as supplementary information indicating the magnitude and uncertainty of the observed associations. These analyses were not primarily intended for formal determination of statistical significance.

Subsequently, the temporal trajectories of each indicator plotted against elapsed days are shown in Figures 5-8. For the indicators measured three times daily (left, right, and bilateral mean tympanic temperature; subjective head heat sensation score; fatigue score; pain score; sternocleidomastoid tension score; subjective psychological distress score; and axillary body temperature during part of the observation period), the daily median was used as the representative value to enhance visual clarity. The missing data observed in the latter part of the tympanic temperature series resulted from the exclusion of measurements obtained prior to probe cover replacement.

Axillary body temperature was not measured continuously on a daily basis but was recorded intermittently to confirm the presence or absence of systemic fever. Periods in which measurements were obtained consecutively are shown as lines, whereas isolated measurements are displayed as individual points. The sternocleidomastoid tension score and subjective psychological distress score were measured only during the latter part of the observation period. Because of the shorter measurement duration, the x-axis for these indicators begins at day 85, differing from the other indicators.

These graphs present observational findings from a single case. The apparent time-series trends may have been influenced by symptoms and measurement conditions.

Figure 5. Temporal Changes in Left, Right, and Bilateral Mean Tympanic Temperature

Note: Left and right tympanic temperatures and bilateral mean tympanic temperature were measured three times per day, and the median value for each day was plotted as the representative value in consideration of visual clarity. Missing data in the latter part of the tympanic temperature record are due to the exclusion of measurements obtained before replacement of the probe cover. This graph represents observations from a single case, and temporal trends may be influenced by symptoms and measurement conditions.

Figure 6. Temporal Changes in Bilateral Mean Tympanic Temperature and Axillary Body Temperature

Note: Bilateral mean tympanic temperature was measured three times per day, and the median value for each day was plotted as the representative value in consideration of visual clarity. Axillary temperature was measured irregularly; segments with consecutive measurements over certain periods are shown as lines, whereas independently measured values are shown as points. Missing data in the latter part of the tympanic temperature record are due to the exclusion of measurements obtained before replacement of the probe cover. This graph represents observations from a single case, and temporal trends may be influenced by measurement conditions and symptom variability.

Figure 7. Temporal Changes in Symptom Scores

Note: Subjective head heat sensation score, pain score, and fatigue score were measured three times per day, and the median value for each day was plotted as the representative value in consideration of visual clarity. As this graph represents observations from a single case, temporal trends may be influenced by measurement conditions and changes in symptoms.

Figure 8. Temporal Changes in Sternocleidomastoid tension score and Subjective psychological distress score During the Last 1.5 Months of Observation

Note: Sternocleidomastoid tension score and subjective psychological distress score were measured only during the latter approximately 1.5-month period; therefore, the horizontal axis begins at day 85 due to the shorter measurement period. These scores were measured three times per day, and the median value for each day was plotted as the representative value in consideration of visual clarity. As this graph represents observations from a single case, temporal trends may be influenced by measurement conditions and changes in symptoms.

3. Correlation Analysis Between Lemborexant Dose and Elapsed Days

Because lemborexant dose was recorded once daily, its association with elapsed days was evaluated using Spearman’s rank correlation coefficient. The analysis demonstrated a negative correlation between lemborexant dose and elapsed days ($\rho = -0.653$, $p = 1.15 \times 10^{-17}$).

A bar graph illustrating lemborexant dose (y-axis) against elapsed days (x-axis) is presented in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Temporal Changes in Daily Lemborexant Dose

Note: Lemborexant dose(mg) during the observation period is shown on a daily basis. Dose values were discrete (0, 1.25, 2.5 mg) and recorded once daily at night. A value of 0 mg indicates no administration. There were no missing days.

4. Tympanic Temperature and Visual Changes in the External Auditory Canal

During the observation period, there were time points at which the trends of symptom scores and tympanic temperature did not appear to correspond. At such time points, the probe cover of the ear thermometer was first replaced to improve measurement conditions. If the correspondence between symptom scores and measured values remained unclear, supplementary observation of the external auditory canal was performed using a consumer-grade camera-equipped ear pick.

External auditory canal imaging was performed not only when discrepancies between symptoms and measured values were suspected but also at several time points when the measurements appeared stable, for comparison. The assessment of correspondence between measured values and symptom scores was not based on predefined statistical criteria and relied on the author's longitudinal subjective assessment.

Representative still images of the external auditory canal at selected time points are shown in Figure 10. At a time point when the correspondence between symptom scores and tympanic temperature appeared unclear (A), clear identification of structures presumed to correspond

to the tympanic membrane was not always possible, even after adjusting the viewing angle. In contrast, at a time point when the trends of symptom scores and tympanic temperature appeared relatively consistent (B), regions presumed to represent the tympanic membrane were partially visible in the images, covering approximately 50% of the presumed tympanic membrane area.

It is important to note that observations of the external auditory canal were not conducted continuously throughout the entire study period, and the findings presented here represent only selected time points. No quantitative or systematic analysis was performed to evaluate the relationship between changes in the shape of the external auditory canal and tympanic temperature measurements. Although the observations were recorded in video format, this paper presents still images from time points deemed representative by the author.

Figure 10. Representative images of the external auditory canal obtained using a camera-equipped ear pick

(A)

(B)

Note: Images of the external auditory canal at time points when the correspondence between symptom scores and tympanic membrane temperature appeared unclear (A) and relatively consistent (B) are shown. At (A), changing the viewing angle did not allow clear identification of structures presumed to represent the tympanic membrane. In contrast, at (B), structures presumed to correspond to the tympanic membrane were partially visible within the canal. These images are presented for illustrative purposes only to explore potential effects of measurement conditions on tympanic membrane temperature readings; observations of the external auditory canal were not conducted systematically throughout the entire observation period.

5. Photographic Assessment of Skeletal Alignment

In the present case, skeletal alignment was evaluated using back photographs as a supplementary indicator of postural changes. Some photographic data were obtained prior to the initiation of body temperature and symptom score recordings; therefore, they were not included in the statistical analyses and are presented for descriptive purposes only as supplemental information on temporal morphological changes.

Representative back photographs were obtained at approximately 1 month, 6 months, and 14.5 months after the initiation of electric massage and are shown in Figures 11-13. In each figure, a reference line approximating the spinal axis, based on the visually identified alignment of the spinous processes, is indicated in panel (A). In panel (B), lines connecting surface markers are shown, with the corresponding angular measurements overlaid. A summary of the angular measurements at each time point is provided in Table 4. For cervical, thoracic, and lumbar angles, as well as some surface-based indices, differences of several degrees were observed between time points; however, no statistical analyses were performed to evaluate these changes.

Figure 11. Back photograph approximately 1 month after the start of electric massage (before the start of tympanic temperature and other observations)

Figure 12. Back photograph approximately 6 months after the start of electric massage

(A)

(B)

Figure 13. Back photograph approximately 14.5 months after the start of electric massage

(A)

(B)

Table 4. Skeletal alignment angles at each time point after the introduction of electric massage

Measurement	~1 month after introduction	~6 months after introduction	~14.5 months after introduction
Cervical spine angle	171°	177°	176°
Thoracic spine angle	164°	175°	170°
Lumbar spine angle	165°	167°	173°
Angle between the line connecting the inferior angles of the scapulae and the horizontal line	5.4°	0.48°	2.9°
Angle between the line connecting bilateral lateral abdominal contour inflection points and the horizontal line	11.5°	8.7°	8.5°
Angle between the line connecting the highest points of the iliac crests and the horizontal line	2.3°	1.05°	0.86°

6. Diary

Diary entries recorded during the observation period were used exclusively to identify the timing of ear thermometer probe cover replacements. The diary data were not used for symptom evaluation or other analytical purposes.

Discussion

1. Positioning of the Study and Interpretive Framework

1.1 Nature of the Study (Single-Case Self-Observation Study)

This study represents a long-term observational investigation based on systematic self-monitoring of a single individual. The individual experienced persistent fatigue, pain, sleep disturbance, and cognitive symptoms described as “brain fog.” Prior to the initiation of the formal observation period, self-care using a commercially available electric massage device

had already been introduced. The objective of this study was to systematically document the temporal course of daily life and symptom fluctuations, including self-care practices such as electric massage, without prespecifying causal assumptions. Accordingly, the findings should be interpreted as descriptive and hypothesis-generating in nature.

The data from the observation period used in this study were obtained approximately 10 months after the initiation of electric massage therapy and therefore do not represent baseline measurements. Accordingly, the symptom changes observed during the study period may reflect gradual fluctuations that occurred after the start of electric massage, as well as transient changes and intra-day or inter-day variability.

In this study, tympanic temperature, axillary body temperature, subjective head heat sensation score, fatigue score, pain score, sternocleidomastoid tension score, subjective psychological distress score, lemborexant dose, and photographic records of posterior skeletal alignment were collected longitudinally. In addition, to examine measurement conditions and potential sources of variability in tympanic temperature readings, supplementary observations of the external auditory canal were conducted using a consumer-grade camera-equipped ear pick.

Measures obtained over approximately 4.5 months were supplemented by additional variables that were introduced during the observation period and collected for approximately 1.5 months. Although some time points included data for all variables, complete data spanning the entire observation period were not available for every measure. Consequently, the time-series structure was partially unbalanced, and simple time-series or correlation analyses require cautious interpretation.

This case was not intended to identify a specific diagnostic category, evaluate treatment effects, or propose a particular hypothesis. Rather, its purpose was to document, as accurately as possible, the subjective and objective changes observed under conditions characterized by marked symptom fluctuations.

In this study, statistical analyses were used as a tool to organize the variability structure of the multi-indicator data obtained during the observation period and to minimize subjective interpretation. Specifically, p-values and false discovery rate (FDR)-adjusted q-values were not used as criteria for determining statistical significance; instead, the numerical results were presented solely as descriptive information to supplement the observed findings.

It may be considered that the significance of this study lies in its inclusion of intra-day and

day-to-day fluctuations, which are often difficult to capture in routine outpatient care or cross-sectional assessments.

1.2 Functional Capacity During the Observation Period and Research Environment

Throughout the observation period, the participant's physical and cognitive functional capacity exhibited substantial intra-day and day-to-day fluctuations. The writing of this manuscript and the data analyses were feasible only during limited periods within the observation phase and could not be performed on a continuous or daily basis. In practice, days on which cognitively demanding work was possible were limited to approximately 10 days per month.

In addition, the recording and analytical procedures in this study were conducted during periods when temporary assistance with daily living was available from family members. These forms of support were not intended as research interventions or as measures to influence symptom changes; rather, they constituted environmental conditions that made the maintenance of daily life and the execution of recording activities physically feasible. These contextual factors should be taken into account when interpreting the findings.

In this study, the relationship between bilateral mean tympanic temperature and each measured indicator was examined descriptively. The findings suggested positive associations between bilateral mean tympanic temperature and the subjective head heat sensation score, fatigue score, pain score, and axillary body temperature. In contrast, no consistent association was descriptively observed between bilateral mean tympanic temperature and the subjective psychological distress score or the dose of lemborexant.

These findings suggest that, in this case, tympanic temperature appeared to fluctuate in parallel with physical symptoms, particularly subjective indicators such as heat sensation, pain, and fatigue. However, these relationships were derived from observations in a single case and may have been influenced by measurement conditions and potential measurement error. Therefore, caution is warranted in their interpretation. Considerations regarding measurement conditions are discussed below.

2.2 Longitudinal trends of each indicator during the observation period

In this study, associations between each indicator and measurement order or elapsed days were examined descriptively within the observation period.

During the approximately 4.5-month observation period, the subjective head heat sensation score, pain score, and fatigue score showed patterns suggestive of positive associations with measurement order. Interpretation of the relationship between tympanic temperature and measurement order is limited by the concentration of missing values in the latter half of the observation period, resulting from the exclusion of data obtained before probe cover replacement. In contrast, no clear association was observed between measurement order and right or left tympanic temperature, bilateral mean tympanic temperature, or axillary body temperature. The dose of lemborexant showed a pattern suggestive of a negative association with elapsed days. It should be noted that axillary body temperature contained a substantial proportion of missing values; therefore, its interpretation requires caution.

Regarding the sternocleidomastoid tension score and the subjective psychological distress score, which were introduced later and measured during the final approximately 1.5 months of the observation period, no clear association with measurement order was observed. The relatively short measurement period for these indicators may have limited the ability to detect potential temporal changes.

Positive correlations with measurement order or elapsed days may suggest a tendency for the respective indicators to increase over the course of the observation period, whereas negative correlations may suggest a tendency to decrease. However, such associations do not necessarily indicate simple worsening or improvement of symptoms and should be interpreted within the broader observational context.

These findings suggest limitations in evaluating symptom improvement or worsening based solely on simple temporal trends. In particular, temporal fluctuations in symptom scores may reflect the influence of multiple external factors, such as changes in physical activity levels, seasonal effects, and short-term symptom fluctuations. The potential impact of these factors on the interpretation of the results will be addressed in a later section.

2.3 Consideration of Measurement Error

Tympanic temperature measurement requires careful consideration of potential errors related to measurement conditions. In this case, several factors were considered as possible sources of variability in the recorded values, including the condition of the probe cover of the ear thermometer, the anatomical characteristics of the external auditory canal, and the measurement angle. At certain time points, inconsistencies between tympanic temperature and symptom scores were observed sporadically. It was not straightforward to determine whether these discrepancies reflected physiological fluctuations or measurement-related factors.

In the present study, to assess the plausibility of the recorded values, potential device-related factors—particularly the probe cover—were examined first. When these factors did not sufficiently account for the observed findings, additional observations of the external auditory canal structure were conducted.

2.3.1 Frequency of Probe Cover Replacement for the Ear Thermometer

In this study, the probe cover of the ear thermometer was replaced multiple times during the observation period. According to the product information provided by the manufacturer, the probe cover is considered a consumable item, and prompt replacement is recommended when visible contamination or damage is observed. Furthermore, even contamination or minor defects that are not readily detectable by visual inspection may affect measurement accuracy. For this reason, regular replacement is generally recommended to help maintain measurement reliability.

During periods in which measurements were continued without replacement of the probe cover, the recorded values tended to be relatively lower. Although no formal statistical analysis was conducted to evaluate this observation, several instances were noted in which the measured temperature increased immediately after the probe cover was replaced with a new one and the measurement was repeated.

The exact timing of the first probe cover replacement could not be determined, as no precise record was retained. However, the date of the second replacement was identifiable based on diary records. Accordingly, data obtained during a defined period (approximately one week) prior to the second replacement were excluded from all analyses in consideration of potential measurement error. Thereafter, measurements were continued with probe covers being

replaced approximately once per month.

2.3.2 Observation of the external auditory canal using a camera-equipped ear pick

When the relationship between tympanic temperature and symptom scores remained difficult to interpret even after replacing the probe cover, supplementary observation of the external auditory canal using a camera-equipped ear pick was conducted. Imaging was performed not only at time points where the correspondence between symptom scores and measurement values was unclear, but also at several time points when the measurements appeared relatively stable, for comparison purposes. The evaluation of the clarity of correspondence between measurement values and symptom scores was not defined statistically, and relied on the author's subjective, longitudinal observations.

In the observation of the external auditory canal, tympanic membrane identification was difficult at time points when the correspondence between symptom scores and tympanic membrane temperature appeared unclear. In contrast, at time points when the progression of symptom scores and tympanic membrane temperature appeared relatively concordant, approximately 50% of the tympanic membrane could be visualized. These findings suggest that factors such as the shape of the external auditory canal, measurement angle, and measurement technique may introduce errors in tympanic membrane temperature assessment.

The observation of the external auditory canal was not conducted continuously throughout the entire study period, and the captured images represent only selected time points. No quantitative or comprehensive evaluation was performed regarding the relationship between changes in the external auditory canal shape and tympanic membrane temperature measurements.

2.3.3 Overall Consideration of Measurement Error

When the relationship between tympanic temperature and symptom scores remained difficult to interpret even after probe cover replacement, supplementary observation of the external auditory canal using a camera-equipped ear pick was conducted. Imaging was performed not only at time points when the correspondence between symptom scores and measurement values appeared unclear, but also at several time points when the measurements appeared relatively stable, for comparison purposes. The assessment of the clarity of correspondence

between measurement values and symptom scores was not defined using statistical criteria and relied on the author's subjective longitudinal observations.

During observation of the external auditory canal, identification of the tympanic membrane was difficult at time points when the correspondence between symptom scores and tympanic temperature appeared unclear. In contrast, at time points when the trajectories of symptom scores and tympanic temperature appeared relatively concordant, approximately half of the tympanic membrane could be visualized. These findings suggest that factors such as the shape of the external auditory canal, measurement angle, and measurement technique may contribute to measurement error in tympanic temperature assessment.

Observation of the external auditory canal was not conducted continuously throughout the entire study period, and the captured images represent selected time points only. No quantitative or comprehensive evaluation was performed regarding the relationship between changes in external auditory canal morphology and tympanic temperature measurements.

2.4 Photographic Evaluation of Skeletal Alignment

In this case, back photographs were intermittently obtained from before the start of the observation period through its end for the supplementary purpose of assessing changes in trunk and pelvic alignment during continued use of the electric massage device, as well as subjective symptoms of pain and fatigue associated with muscle tension and stiffness. Because some of these photographs were acquired prior to the initiation of body temperature and symptom score recordings, they were not included in statistical analyses and are presented solely as reference information regarding temporal morphological changes.

In the photographic evaluation, variability was observed in angle indices derived from surface markers; however, these changes did not necessarily correspond to the overall visual impression of the back or to the subject's perceived bodily sensations. Even at time points when angle changes were detected, trunk asymmetry remained visually apparent.

Based on diary records and subjective impressions, muscle tension and stiffness around the left trunk and pelvis fluctuated both across days and within individual days, and difficulties in maintaining a seated posture changed reversibly. In the early observation period, reduced physical activity was noted, and the influence of trunk muscle weakness could not be excluded. However, later in the observation period, a trend toward recovery of physical activity was

observed. These symptom fluctuations cannot be explained solely by muscle weakness and may suggest the involvement of muscle tension distribution and postural control mechanisms.

The angle measurements used in this study represent a simplified evaluation based on surface morphology and differ fundamentally from radiographic assessments such as Cobb angle measurements. The obtained angles do not directly represent spinal deviation and may be influenced by posture and imaging conditions.

Taken together, the use of photographic records in addition to symptom scores and physiological indicators may have provided complementary information on aspects of physical condition that are difficult to capture using numerical indices alone. However, this evaluation has no diagnostic significance, and future studies should integrate assessments of muscle tone and functional measures to achieve a more comprehensive understanding.

3. Interpretation of Results and Methodological Considerations

3.1 Characteristics as a Self-Observation Study (N = 1)

This case represents a self-observation study with N = 1, and caution is required when considering generalizability or drawing causal inferences from the findings. Throughout the observation period, self-care practices—including the use of an electric massage device—were continued as part of daily life. The present study was not designed to evaluate or demonstrate the effects of electric massage. Symptom scores and subjective assessments were based on the participant's own judgment at the time of recording, and the influence of subjectivity in the evaluation process cannot be excluded.

At the same time, efforts were made to record changes in daily life longitudinally, including symptom scores, physiological indicators, and photographic records of skeletal alignment, alongside continued self-care practices. Although such longitudinal self-observation is not intended to establish causal relationships, it may provide exploratory information for describing intra-individual fluctuations in physical condition and patterns of association among measured indicators.

3.2 Activity capacity during the observation period and considerations for result interpretation

During the observation period, the participant was able to perform mild activities of daily living and limited cognitive tasks (e.g., manuscript writing). However, these activities were not feasible on a daily basis, and the number of days on which they could be performed was limited to approximately 10 days per month. Marked within-day and between-day variability in physical and cognitive activity capacity was observed.

Recordings and analyses were conducted during periods when temporary support from family members was available. These supports did not constitute research interventions or attempts to modify symptoms; rather, they provided environmental conditions that made daily living and data recording physically feasible. Accordingly, the data were collected under a certain level of supportive conditions, which should be considered when interpreting the results.

The findings therefore do not reflect a consistently stable level of activity, but are based on recordings obtained under intermittently fluctuating activity capacity. In addition, there were periods during which probe covers for the tympanic thermometer could not be replaced at the recommended frequency. This occurred because severe symptoms during the observation period substantially limited the ability to carry out routine daily tasks.

These limitations were not the result of intentional restrictions in research procedures, but rather arose from the practical constraints inherent in conducting a self-observation study under conditions of severe symptoms. Such constraints are likely unavoidable in long-term, single-case, home-based self-observation studies and should be taken into account when interpreting the findings.

3.3 Considerations on Qualitative Changes in Subjective Assessments

In this case, the participant had experienced chronic fatigue for approximately ten years prior to the observation period, followed by the emergence of pain, yet no definitive diagnosis was established in clinical settings. Subjective symptoms such as fatigue and pain are inherently difficult to compare across individuals and may fluctuate over long periods in terms of perceived validity and severity. Therefore, a tendency to underestimate symptoms prior to the observation period cannot be excluded. This context may have influenced the assignment of symptom scores during the initial phase of observation.

Throughout the observation period, the participant repeatedly engaged in self-care practices, including the use of an electric massage device, and experienced transient exacerbations and relative alleviations of symptoms. Through this repeated experience, the participant may have gradually become better able to recognize and differentiate between relatively lower- and higher-burden bodily states. This process may reflect not necessarily a reduction in the absolute magnitude of pain, but rather an adjustment in the perception and relative evaluation of sensory stimuli.

As a result, the participant may have become able to assess and quantify fatigue and pain using more concrete and internally consistent criteria. In this context, increases in symptom scores observed during the observation period may not solely represent simple worsening of symptoms, but may also reflect changes in subjective evaluation standards—so-called recalibration.

Such qualitative changes in subjective evaluation constitute not only an important limitation of the present study, but also a methodological challenge inherent in long-term self-observation research. At the same time, documenting the gradual refinement of awareness of bodily states highlights aspects that are difficult to capture in short-term observations or routine outpatient settings, and may represent one potential value of patient-centered research.

In addition, in this case, the pain score did not directly reflect the intensity of stimuli applied during self-care and may therefore not fully capture changes in symptoms. This issue is further addressed in the following section.

3.4 Considerations on the Temporal Changes in Pain, Fatigue, and Nonspecific Physical Responses

Long-term changes in pain and fatigue scores in this case were analyzed statistically over an approximately 4.5-month observation period. In contrast, the short-term changes immediately following individual massage sessions and considerations related to the intensity of massage stimuli, as described below, were not subjected to statistical analysis and are based on the author's subjective observations and diary records.

At the early stages of using the electric massage device, even low-intensity vibratory stimulation elicited pain sensations. During the massage sessions, a tendency toward pain

alleviation was observed, followed by a reappearance of pain the next day, resulting in a repeated wave-like pattern. With continued use of the massage device, the initial pain under the same stimulus conditions gradually decreased. The intensity of the massage was progressively increased as part of routine self-care.

In this case, transient increases in pain and fatigue scores (lasting approximately 1–2 weeks) were repeatedly observed, coinciding with the initial use of the electric massage device or the commencement of massage on new body regions. Additionally, changes in muscle tension at specific sites were occasionally associated with the emergence of pain or discomfort in other areas. These short-term fluctuations in symptom scores may have been influenced by multiple factors, including excessive stimulation, changes in stimulation site, and variations in physical activity; however, this study was not able to identify the specific contributing factors. These observations suggest that such self-care interventions may involve a certain degree of uncertainty or risk.

Furthermore, in this case, the pain score reflected the subjectively perceived intensity of pain at each time point and did not serve as an indicator of the stimulation intensity applied during self-care. Consequently, even if the perceived pain in response to the same or greater stimulation had relatively decreased, this change might not have been fully captured by the pain score.

Although these symptoms were not included in the quantitative analysis, the diary records sporadically documented a variety of additional symptoms beyond pain and fatigue, including headache, ocular pain, abdominal pain, urinary urgency, and small raised rashes. These symptoms were sometimes temporally associated with massage of the neck, abdomen, lower abdomen, or back, or with periods during which palpable muscle hardening was present; however, no statistical analysis was conducted. These observations are limited to descriptive records and do not imply causal relationships.

Taken together, the temporal fluctuations of pain, fatigue, and other non-specific somatic symptoms in this case exhibited a complex course, including discrepancies between the applied stimulus conditions and subjective evaluations. These findings suggest that univocal interpretation based solely on symptom scores is inherently limited.

3.5 Overall Symptom Score Variability and the Relationship with Activity and Self-Care

Throughout the observation period, the participant subjectively perceived changes in bodily mobility, the quality of discomfort, and daily physical activity compared with the early phase following the introduction of the electric massage device. However, these perceived changes were not clearly reflected in pain or fatigue scores. Diary records also suggested that the number of days with possible physical activity increased during the latter part of the observation period, indicating that elevations in symptom scores did not necessarily correspond to overall functional decline. Nevertheless, since not all symptom fluctuations coincided temporally with increased activity or massage sessions, interpretations must be made with caution.

In this study, physical activity was not quantitatively recorded, and diary entries were not treated as analyzable variables. Therefore, it was not possible to statistically assess the relationship between symptom scores and physical activity or self-care. This limitation makes it difficult to rigorously distinguish between the natural fluctuations of symptoms and transient responses associated with physical activity or self-care.

In addition, the end of the observation period occurred during the winter, and subjectively, symptom scores may have increased due to cold exposure and the augmented muscle tension associated with layering clothing. However, based on the author's own perception, stiffness and discomfort appeared reduced compared with the previous winter (prior to the observation period), suggesting that the observed increase in symptom scores did not necessarily reflect an overall decline in function.

On the other hand, since symptoms persisted and self-care was ongoing at the time of manuscript preparation, it should be noted that the course described in this study represents an observation captured at an intermediate stage of the underlying condition.

Taken together, the fluctuations in symptom scores observed in this case should not be interpreted simply as worsening or improvement. Rather, they represent measures that require contextual consideration, including the participant's physical activity levels and self-care practices. In future patient-centered studies of this type, recording both symptom scores and indicators of physical activity or bodily load may allow for a more refined understanding of the dynamics of the underlying condition.

3.6 Integrated Consideration of General Physical Discomfort Observed Across Multiple Measures

In this section, we consider the possibility that, in this case, multiple measures—including tympanic temperature, symptom scores, lemborexant usage, skeletal alignment, and diary records—were recorded in parallel not as isolated phenomena, but as complementary indicators that collectively capture aspects of the participant’s overall physical state that could not be fully represented by symptom scores alone.

In this case, the physical discomfort consistently experienced by the participant was not limited to simple pain or fatigue, but also included sensations described as “tightness,” “resistance during movement,” and a “general sense of stiffness and heaviness.” These sensations were perceived not only at rest or during sleep, but also in conjunction with difficulty in movement and easy fatigability during activity. Furthermore, although no statistical verification was performed, increases in tympanic temperature, symptom scores, and changes in lemborexant usage were subjectively observed by the participant to coincide temporally with periods when these physical discomforts were most strongly perceived.

On the other hand, this study did not directly measure muscle activity, muscle stiffness, neural activity, autonomic nervous system indices, or circulatory parameters. Therefore, the observed fluctuations cannot be attributed to a single pathophysiological mechanism based solely on the indicators used in this study. Rather, this case suggests that the participant’s bodily state can simultaneously fluctuate across multiple layers, including temperature, physiological indices, subjective symptoms, and posture/alignment. In the future, constructing a set of integrated indicators capable of capturing these multiple dimensions may be important for more precisely characterizing complex pathophysiological dynamics.

3.7 Ethical and Procedural Considerations Specific to Single-Subject Research

In this study, data recording was conducted during periods in which temporary daily living support was provided by family members. These forms of support were not introduced as research interventions, nor were they intended to modify symptomatology. Rather, they constituted environmental conditions that enabled the continuation of daily life and made sustained self-recording feasible.

It should be noted that such contextual factors may indirectly influence the participant’s physical or psychological state. However, in this case, the support was not systematically

manipulated or structured for research purposes, and no attempt was made to evaluate its effects. The study therefore reflects observations made under naturally occurring living conditions, albeit within a temporarily supported domestic environment.

4. Limitations

This study was based on a single case, which substantially limits the generalizability of the findings. All observations and measurements were performed by the participant, resulting in inherent constraints on measurement consistency and objectivity. Subjective elements were inevitably included in symptom scores and muscle tension assessments.

Symptom fluctuations may have been influenced by multiple factors, including sleep, psychological state, lifestyle habits, seasonal conditions, and self-care practices. Because these variables were neither systematically controlled nor quantitatively measured, clear causal relationships cannot be established. Accordingly, the findings should be regarded as exploratory and hypothesis-generating rather than confirmatory.

It should also be noted that self-care, including the use of an electric massage device, had already been initiated at the start of the observation period. Therefore, the data do not represent a strict baseline but rather reflect changes occurring after the introduction of self-care. In addition, to prioritize personal privacy, certain background information was intentionally reported only in limited form, further restricting the generalizability of the results.

This case was conducted under circumstances in which continuous visits to medical institutions were difficult, and care was largely self-managed. Consequently, the study lacks external clinical verification and relies heavily on subjective evaluation. Moreover, the purpose of this report was not to classify the case within a specific diagnostic category, but to descriptively document temporal symptom changes. No causal inference or generalization is intended, and the results should be interpreted strictly as descriptive observations within a single individual.

5. Implications for Future Research

In future patient-centered studies, longitudinal recording of not only symptom scores but also physical activity, sleep parameters, load intensity, and seasonal factors may allow for a more precise interpretation of symptom fluctuations. Furthermore, standardization of measurement conditions to minimize measurement error, as well as the concurrent use of multiple indicators, is considered important.

Conclusion

In this case, longitudinal recording of daily symptom changes and physiological indicators was conducted over approximately 4.5 months under continued self-care, including the use of an electric massage device. The findings demonstrated that tympanic temperature, symptom scores, and postural or alignment-related information fluctuated in a temporally overlapping manner. This pattern suggests that changes in bodily state may be more comprehensively characterized through multiple complementary indicators rather than a single measure alone. Structural factors potentially influencing the interpretation of tympanic temperature, such as ear canal morphology, were also examined, and possible measurement error was considered.

However, this study was based on a single-subject self-observation design with inherent constraints in measurement conditions and reliance on self-managed care. Accordingly, the generalizability of the findings is limited.

This report may be positioned as an illustrative case demonstrating the integrated documentation of symptom fluctuations and self-care processes. In future patient-centered research, the development of frameworks that integrate subjective evaluations, physiological indicators, and physical activity measures may offer new perspectives for understanding chronic symptoms that are otherwise difficult to diagnose or characterize.

Conflict of Interest

The author declares no conflicts of interest related to this study.